

ANALYSIS OF THE DYNAMICS OF TREATMENT OF INFILTRATIVE TUBERCULOSIS WITH DRUGS OF THE 5TH LINE. 1 TRIMESTER**Zhakenova U.,***Doctor - phthisiatrician of the 1st category of the 2nd therapeutic department of the KSE "Kostanay Regional Center for Phthisiopulmonology" (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)***Kayny Sh.,***Doctor - phthisiatrician of the 2nd therapeutic department of the KSE "Kostanay regional center of phthisiopulmonology" (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)***Aida Zh.,***Doctor - phthisiatrician of the 2nd therapeutic department of the KSE "Kos Sazanov tanay regional center of phthisiopulmonology" (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)***Kushenova S.,***Doctor - phthisiatrician of the 2nd therapeutic department of the KSE "Kostanay regional center of phthisiopulmonology" (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)***Gorbenko M.,***Candidate of Philology, Associate Professor of the Department of Humanities, Kostanay Socio-Technical University named after Academician Z. Aldamzhar (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)***Iskakov I.,***Head of the 2nd therapeutic department of the KSE "Kostanay regional center of phthisiopulmonology", doctor - phthisiopulmonology of the highest category (Kostanay, Kazakhstan)*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7997528>**Abstract**

This article analyzes the dynamics of the treatment of infiltrative tuberculosis with drugs of the 5th line. 1 trimester

Keywords: infiltrative tuberculosis, anti-tuberculosis drugs, drug resistance, conversion, dynamics.

Introduction

The epidemiological situation of tuberculosis in the Republic of Kazakhstan today is characterized by a decrease in the incidence and a simultaneous increase in the number of patients with drug-resistant (DR) tuberculosis. The Republic of Kazakhstan is among the 18 WHO priority countries in terms of multidrug resistance (MDR-TB). In general, in the Kostanay region, against the background of a decrease in the incidence of tuberculosis, there is a clear trend towards an increase in the number of patients with primary MDR-TB. In the period 2020-2022, the decrease in the incidence of tuberculosis ranged from 74.6% to 64.7% per 100,000 population. At the same time, the number of patients with primary MDR TB increased from 15% to 25.3% over the same time period. The treatment of DR-TB is complicated in terms of designing a treatment program: it is lengthy, requiring patients to take a course of chemotherapy for up to two years, while experiencing the side effects of medications.

The aim of the study is to analyze the dynamics of treatment when taking drugs of the 5th line in the 1st trimester.

Materials and methods of research: retrospective analysis of patients' medical records.

Recipients: a group of patients - 10 people (men) from 24 to 56 years old. Weight category of human is from 40 to 72 kg.

Anti-tuberculosis drugs of the 5th line: Bedaquelin, Delamanid, Clofazimine, Linezomide. Levofloxacin and Cycloserine are added or excluded depending on the treatment regimen and compliance with the protocol.

Treatment of patients with infiltrative form of tuberculosis is carried out under the supervision of a phthisiatrician, who is fully responsible for the correctness and effectiveness of treatment. The entire course of treatment of patients with infiltrative tuberculosis, or its individual stages, is allowed to be carried out in a hospital with a round-the-clock or only day stay, as well as in a sanatorium and on an outpatient basis.

Table 1

№	Treatment regimen	Anamnesis	Dynamics of the first trimester		Outcome
			negative	positive	
S. (44 years old, weight 72 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz. Bedaquiline 2 tab. -200 mg Levofloxacin 4 tabl - 1000 mg Cycloserine 4 tablets - 1000 mg Linezolid - 1 tablet 600 mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100 mg	Complaints of cough with mucopurulent sputum, general weakness, periodic sweating.		+	During treatment, there is a positive trend due to the conversion of sputum, X-ray picture. There are no complaints. I put on weight 10 kg, 82 kg. X-ray dynamics is positive due to compaction of foci.
B. (55 years old, weight 65 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6) Dlm (6)CsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tablets 200 mg Delamanid 4 tablets 200 mg Cycloserine 3 tablets 750 mg Linezolid 1 tablet - 600 mg. Clofazimine - 1 tab. 100 mg.	Complaints of cough with mucopurulent sputum.		+	During the treatment period, there is a positive trend. There are no complaints. Gained weight 4 kg, 69 kg. Sputum conversion achieved. X-ray dynamics is positive due to compaction of foci.
K (29 years old, weight 60 kg))	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20 BdqLfxCfzLzdCs Bedaquiline 2 tablets 200 mg Levofloxacin 4 tablets 1000 mg Cycloserine 3 tablets, 750 mg Linezolid 1 tablet - 600 mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg.	Complaints of cough with mucopurulent sputum, general weakness.	No sputum conversion. X-ray dynamics is negative due to increased infiltration.	There are no complaints. Gained weight 2 kg, 62 kg.	There is a negative trend.
A (34 years old, weight 47 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 3 tabs 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints of cough with mucopurulent sputum, single streaks of blood persist		+	He gained weight by 8 kg, sputum smear conversion was achieved after 1, 2, 3 months of treatment, R. dynamics + compaction of foci.
H (51 years old, weight 58kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 3tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints of cough with mucus sputum		+	Complaints of cough with mucus sputum + Gained weight by 2 kg, sputum smear conversion achieved after 2.3 months of treatment, P. dynamics + compaction of foci, decrease in infiltration
F (24 years old, weight 46 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg	Complaints of cough with mucus sputum		+	Gained weight by 3 kg, sputum smear conversion achieved after 1,2,3

	Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 3tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg				months of treatment, R. dynamics + compaction of foci, decrease in infiltration
K. (47years old, weight70 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 3tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints at admission: cough with mucopurulent sputum, shortness of breath at rest, severe weakness, sweating, swelling in the legs, weight loss up to 20 kg within 3 months, fever up to 38.-39.0*c in within 3 weeks.	-		During treatment, the patient gained 2 kg in weight. Complaints of shortness of breath during physical exertion, weakness persist. The conversion of sputum smear by bacterioscopy and bacterial culture was not achieved after 1,2,3 months of treatment. Radiologically, there is a negative trend due to an increase in infiltration.
T. (41 years old weight-40kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 2tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints of frequent cough with mucopurulent sputum, general weakness.		+	During the treatment, there is a positive clinical and radiological dynamics. Achieved sputum smear conversion by bacterioscopy and bacterial culture after the first month of treatment. Gained 7kg in weight.
X. (53 years old Weight - 57 kg)	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 2tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints of frequent cough with mucopurulent sputum, general weakness.		+	During the treatment, there is a positive clinical and radiological dynamics. Sputum smear conversion by bacterioscopy was achieved. Gained 2 kg in weight.
F. 56 years old Weight-55kg	ITR (individual treatment regimen) according to the scheme 20Bdq(6)LfxCsLzdCfz Bedaquiline 2 tabl 100mg Levofloxacin 4 tabs 250mg Cycloserine 3tab 250mg Linezolid 1 tab 600mg Clofazimine 1 tab 100mg	Complaints at admission: general weakness, cough with sputum difficult to separate, moderate shortness of breath, night sweats, loss of appetite, weight loss, fever up to 37.5 C			During the treatment, positive clinical and radiographic dynamics is noted. Conversion of sputum smear by bacterioscopy and bacteriology was achieved. Gained 3 kg in weight.

Conclusion: 8 recipients showed positive dynamics in the form of sputum conversion, clinical and radiological dynamics.

In 2 recipients, a negative trend is observed due to the preservation of bacillus excretion, an increase in infiltration in the lungs.

The organizational form of treatment is determined taking into account the

severity of the course of the disease, the epidemic danger of the patient, the material and living conditions

of his life, the psychological characteristics of the patient, the degree of social adaptation and local conditions. Regardless of the organizational form of treatment, the requirements for the standard (protocol) and control of its implementation, as well as continuity between medical institutions when changing the organizational form of treatment to another, must be observed. Treatment outcomes are evaluated using performance criteria such as:

- clinical (reduction or disappearance of symptoms of intoxication; micro-biological - sputum smear conversion;

-X-ray - reduction of infiltrative-inflammatory changes in the lungs and draw up appropriate documentation.

To assess the effectiveness of each course of chemotherapy, a quarterly pooled analysis using standard definitions of its results, which are carried out by the Central Medical Control Commission (CMCC), is required.

In the next article, we will present an analysis of the dynamics of the treatment of infiltrative tuberculosis with drugs of the 5th line of the second trimester.

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HISTORY OF THE FIRST AMIDE LOCAL ANESTHETIC (ON THE 80th ANNIVERSARY OF XYLOCAINE SYNTHESIS)

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